

PARACHOR OF THYMOL, MENTHOL AND *p*-TOLUIDINE IN DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS.

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Parachor of thymol, menthol and *p*-toluidine in nitrobenzene, acetic acid etc. has been determined at different concentrations. It is observed that the values of parachor at temperatures, where these substances exist as liquid and at temperatures where they exist as solids, are practically the same as obtained by solution methods. The Hammick and Andrew's equation, therefore, is applicable both in liquid and solid states for the solutes. The nature of the solvent does not seem to have any appreciable effect on the values of the parachor of solutes. At lower concentrations of the solute the values obtained by Hammick and Andrew's equation show greater variation from the calculated values.

The method employed for determining the parachor in solution is the same as that due to Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 755). Thus

$$P_m = P(1-x) + P_x x \quad \dots (i)$$

$$P_m = \frac{M_m}{(D-d)} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (ii)$$

and $M_m = M_s (1-x) + M_x x \quad \dots (iii)$

Where P_m = parachor of the mixture, P_x = the parachor of the solute, P = the parachor of the solvent, x = the molar fraction of the solute, $(1-x)$ = the molar fraction of the solvent, M_m = the mean molecular weight, D = the density of the solution, γ = surface tension of the solution, M_s = the molecular weight of the solvent and M_x = the molecular weight of the solute.

The value of γ was determined by Jaeger's bubble method. The value of D was found by pycnometer, while the value of d , the density of the vapour of the solvent was neglected. The value of g substituted is 978 dynes/cm. cm. at Indore.

Thymol melts at 50°. It will be observed from the table below that the values determined by keeping the solution below, above and at the melting point of thymol, differ only very slightly. In general it is observed that as the concentration of the solute is decreased the values obtained by Hammick and Andrew's formula deviate more and more from the calculated value (377 for thymol). Temperature seems to have no effect on the value of the parachor.

TABLE I.

Parachor of thymol in nitrobenzene.

$x=0.176.$					$x=0.229$				
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	Temp	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$
40°	1.137	36.16	274.8	373	20°	1.137	38.7	282.6	375
45	1.130	35.9	275.8	373	30	1.129	37.5	283.3	378
50	1.126	35.5	276.2	376	40	1.12	37.4	285.2	386
55	1.121	34.6	275.4	371	50	1.11	35.6	284.5	383
60	1.118	34.8	276.4	377	60	1.105	34.2	282.8	377
$x=0.122.$					$x=0.095.$				
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	Density	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	
20°	1.166	40.9	273.9	401	1.177	39.55	268.0	392	
30	1.157	39.7	274.1	402	1.169	38.72	267.8	389	
40	1.148	37.7	271.9	393	1.158	37.08	267.4	386	
50	1.141	36.1	271.3	388	1.148	36.26	268.4	396	
60	1.131	35.2	272.2	392	1.137	34.55	267.3	385	
70	1.123	34.0	271.6	391	1.132	33.7	267.2	382	
$x=0.214$									
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$					
20°	1.142	37.55	279.9	370					
30	1.132	35.83	278.7	368					
40	1.122	35.20	279.6	371					
50	1.115	34.34	279.0	369					
60	1.107	33.59	280.3	375					
70	1.099	32.84	280.5	376					

TABLE II.

Parachor of thymol in acetic acid.

$x=0.176. P_{calc}=377.0$				
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$
20°	1.022	29.1	174.8	379
30	1.014	27.28	169.4	349
40	1.004	26.64	174.1	375
50	0.9942	25.89	174.5	377
60	0.9855	25.14	174.8	379
70	0.9776	24.39	175.0	380

The values are very good showing that, as in the case of liquid-liquid mixture, where only one liquid is associating, there is no effect on the value of parachor, in the case of solid-liquid solution also, where the liquid is associating, the value of parachor is not affected.

Determination of Parachor of Menthol.—The following structure for menthol is assumed :

TABLE III.
Solvent—Nitrobenzene.

Temp.	$x=0.081.$				$x=0.198.$			
	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$	Density	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$
20°	1.165	36.0	265.3	383				
30	1.158	34.8	263.2	361				
40	1.149	33.59	263.1	360	1.096	31.48	280.0	381
50	1.140	32.3	262.6	354	1.088	30.68	280.0	381
60	1.132	31.56	263.1	360	1.077	28.96	278.6	375
70	...	...	...	...	1.069	28.22	279.6	379
Temp.	$x=0.238.$				$x=0.255.$			
	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$
20°	1.100	32.96	286.8	389	1.094	33.70	289.5	393
30	1.091	32.28	287.6	392	1.084	32.95	290.6	395
40	1.083	31.45	287.6	392	1.076	32.31	291.1	396
50	1.074	30.81	288.7	396	1.066	31.67	292.3	401
60	1.064	31.13	292.1	411*	1.057	30.92	293.1	405
70	1.057	29.85	290.1	403	1.049	30.16	293.6	406
Temp.	$x=0.084.$				$x=0.173.$			
	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_X.$
20°	1.017	25.67	150.7	373	0.9906	28.14	178.1	401
30	1.206	24.88	151.1	378	0.9822	26.43	176.9	394
40	0.9961	23.11	149.5	359*	0.9736	26.74	178.9	406
50	0.9858	22.57	150.5	370	0.9641	24.93	177.5	398
60	0.9757	21.82	149.2	355*	0.9532	23.32	176.7	393
70	0.9650	21.18	151.3	379	0.9446	23.00	177.6	399
80	0.9532	20.36	151.8	386	...	...	...	...

TABLE IV.

Parachor of menthol in carbon tetrachloride.

$x=0.161$	Temp.	Density	γ	$P_M.$	$P_X.$
	20°	1.412	30.81	254.2	438
	30	1.396	29.25	253.9	436
	40	1.384	27.00	252.0	424
	Menthol liquid				
	60	0.856	27.17		416.1
				Calc. parachor	416.1

This value is identical with the value calculated for the formula. Calculated value for the parachor of menthol is 416.1. The results, therefore, are low as given by Hammick and Andrew's formulae and more so, if the concentration of the solute is low. In carbon tetrachloride, however, the values are high.

Parachor of p-toluidine in nitrobenzene.

TABLE V.

$x=0.267.$					$x=0.313.$			
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$
20°	1.128	40.98	270.5	278	1.136	41.73	264.1	284
30	1.122	40.12	269.1	274	1.127	39.90	263.4	282
40	1.114	39.37	271.1	280	1.117	38.08	262.5	279
50	1.106	37.55	270.1	277	1.109	36.38	261.3	275
60	1.097	36.27	269.7	276	1.100	35.63	262.0	277
70	1.087	35.62	270.0	277	1.091	34.87	262.6	279
$x=0.403.$					$x=0.214.$			
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$
20°	1.109	40.12	264.5	279	1.152	37.34	256.0	264
30	1.106	39.15	263.6	278	1.142	36.59	257.6	268
40	1.097	38.41	265.0	280	1.133	35.94	258.3	271
50	1.087	36.71	263.4	275.9	1.124	35.21	259.1	274
60	1.080	35.83	264.3	277	1.115	34.55	260.1	278
70	1.070	35.20	265.1	280	1.107	33.70	259.2	275
$x=0.467.$					$x=0.122.$			
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$
20°	1.100	42.58	266.2	279	1.179	41.61	260.7	301
30	1.092	40.76	266.2	279	1.169	40.87	261.5	306
40	1.084	39.90	266.8	280	1.161	40.12	262.3	315
50	1.076	39.15	268.0	283	1.152	38.94	262.5	316
60	1.064	37.54	268.4	284	1.143	37.12	261.3	305
70	1.057	36.81	268.8	285	1.133	34.63	258.9	287
$x=0.091.$								
Temp.	Density.	$\gamma.$	$P_M.$	$P_x.$				
20°	1.184		43.0	262.8	341			
30	1.174		41.3	262.2	333			
40	1.165		39.48	261.3	324			
50	1.157		37.65	260.1	312			
60	1.149		36.91	260.5	315			
70	1.139		35.20	259.9	309			

The calculated value for the parachor of *p*-toluidine is 275.9. The experimental agreement is excellent at higher concentrations.